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Safety Performance Functions to predict Separation Minima Infringements in en-route airspace

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Abstract. The objective of this methodology is to characterise the safety of air routes under a systematic framework, in terms of Separation Minimum Infringements (SMI) between en-route aircraft based on models known as Safety Performance Functions (SPF). Bayesian Networks have been selected as techniques with high predictive capability and low probability event estimation. Moreover, they allow the integration of knowledge modelling with data inference. It is complex to develop a Bayesian Network model for SMI prediction. It is necessary to integrate the available knowledge about the precursors of SMIs together with the accumulated knowledge from the analysis of the collected data into a conceptual framework. This framework underpinning the Bayesian Network model focuses on the Closest Point of Approach (CPA) analysis and considers the general scenario of aircraft evolution in an air traffic sector. In order to translate this conceptual framework into a set of causal sub-networks, the ATM barrier and event tree models are used.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the aviation industry is undergoing a paradigm shift, evolving from a reactive, compliance-based safety mindset to proactive, performance-based approaches [1]. Stakeholders must monitor, collect and analyse safety-related data and information in order to anticipate and predict actual and emerging risks that could compromise the normal conduct of aviation operations. In this context, statistical analysis and safety assessment must evolve to predict future risks and performance of the air transport network [2].

The objective of this project is to establish a systematic framework for characterising the safety of air routes in terms of loss of separation between aircraft, based on the definition of models known as Predictive Safety Performance Functions (SPF), adapted to the particularities of each airspace, and which take into account the intrinsic characteristics of airspace, such as the routes and sectors involved, aircraft traffic and its evolution and airspace management. Such models, once developed, calibrated and validated, could be extended to other key performance areas in air traffic management, such as capacity, efficiency, etc.

2. Scope

This project adopts a statistical approach little exploited in the ATM domain, which involves modelling aircraft separation losses as count data to develop statistical models. The aim is to estimate and predict the potential loss of separation between aircraft in airspace, depending on the intrinsic characteristics of the route and sector scenario, of the traffic and its evolution and of the airspace management and organisation.

To achieve this overall objective, this project addresses three key challenges,

- Research and application of statistical counting models for the development of ATM SPFs;
- Characterisation of the factors that determine, influence or condition the loss of separation between aircraft in different airspaces;
- Development of a methodology sufficiently open and flexible to allow its extension to other performance measures related to air traffic management such as capacity, efficiency, fairness, flexibility, etc.

3. Methodology

The mathematical models used to predict and explain the occurrence of safety events are called Safety Performance Functions.

Since the total sample of flights in airspace has a very small number of Separation Minima Infringements, traditional approaches lack statistical validity [3]. Therefore, Bayesian Networks are used, which have a high predictive power and are well suited for the estimation of low probability events [4].

Moreover, BNs can integrate expert knowledge with real information extracted directly from the data. This approach of feeding back the available information on the possible causes of SMIs and the knowledge extracted from the project data, especially from the ATCo actions [5], is very useful.

However, this is a complex process and a conceptual framework needs to be defined to frame the Bayesian Network model. This approach is based on the Closest Point of Approach (CPA) [6], considering aircraft pairs of a general scenario and their evolution. Thus, the evolution of each pair of aircraft until they reach their CPA has to be taken into account.

3.1. Initial approach to SPF

A general scenario proposed as an example can be seen in Figure 1. It includes two aircraft pairs and their respective trajectories. The CPA is marked with a red circle.

If ATCo does not intervene on the aircraft pair and therefore the aircraft evolution is not affected, the CPA would be defined as *CPA prior*. However, the actual CPA between the aircraft will be the result of their trajectories after being modified by ATCo and will be defined as *final CPA*.

Therefore, the CPA between a pair of aircraft is considered to be the shortest actual distance between them, expressed as their vertical and horizontal separation.

Figure 1. Conceptual representation of a scenario and its traffic evolution.

Therefore, this approach is based on three main concepts to define the interaction of a pair of aircraft:

- Considering only the initial trajectories, the minimum distance at which the aircraft pair would meet *dCPA prior*.
- Time elapsed between the CPA and the moment when the ATCo gave the last clearance *TLC* [7].
- Considering ATCo action, the minimum distance at which the *dCPA final* aircraft pair would be.

These three elements are implemented in Figure 2. Aircraft are defined as blue dots, as well as their CPA in case of only looking at their initial trajectories (*dCPA*) with a red line. However, one of the functions of the ATCo is to assess whether the *dCPA* is a possible Separation Minima Infringement, in which case they will act on the pair to avoid it.

The distance at which the pair of aircraft would be when the controller acts is defined on the right hand side by *d at TLC*. Therefore, the final CPA at which the pair would cross after the modification in their evolution introduced by the controller would be defined by a green line indicating the *final dCPA*.

Figure 2. *CPA prior vs. CPA final.*

The three concepts outlined above can be modelled as three sub-networks defined according to the precursors influencing each of them and are visualised in Figure 3.

The sub-network defining the CPA priority estimates the probability of vertical and horizontal separation between two aircraft in the case where there is no intervention on the development of their evolution. The estimation will take into account the causal relationships influencing each sub-network.

From this distribution, which is drawn as the output of the sub-network, it is possible to identify cases where the minimum separation distance is below the measures defined as safe minimums: 5NM horizontal and 1000ft vertical. These cases would represent a potential conflict and should therefore be acted upon by the ATCo.

The same concept is extrapolated for the TLC and CPA prior sub-networks. In the TLC sub-network, the time distribution of ATCo actions can be observed.

Finally, the output distribution of the final CPA subnetwork shows how the number of Separation Minima Infringements is reduced thanks to the ATCo's actions.

Figure 3. Proposed conceptual model

The concepts of ATM barrier model and event trees are incorporated into the conceptual approach in order to translate it into a set of causal sub-networks.

3.2. *ATM Barrier Model and Event Tree Analysis*

By means of the ATM barrier model it is possible to observe the evolution of a possible accident, defined by the safety barriers that would have to fail for it to finally occur [8]. These safety barriers divide the control process into different consecutive stages.

The model presented in this study is based on an adaptation of the barrier model presented by Eurocontrol [9], which reflects the stages in the evolution of a possible Separation Minima Infringement and allows the expert knowledge to be brought together with the objective data collected.

Figure 4. ATM Barrier Model

After identifying these safety barriers, the event tree approach is used to complete the translation of the conceptual framework proposed so far into a causal network.

The event tree allows the responses of each node to be evaluated using Boolean logic through a single initiating event, is a top-down modelling technique and facilitates the exploration of the model as a whole [10].

Figure 5 shows the sequence of ATM stages or barriers at the top. It can also be seen the bifurcation that expresses whether the exit from each barrier is a success or a failure. Finally, the conditional probabilities defining each possible combination of the accident evolution can be seen.

Figure 5. Bayesian Network Implementation.

3.3. Bayesian Network definition

Once this level of detail has been reached in describing the conceptual framework and the causal model, it is implemented using Bayesian Networks. Thus, each of the ATM safety barriers presented will be modelled using a Bayesian Network.

The complete proposed large-scale model is depicted in Figure 6. Two types of sub-networks can be identified according to their nature: sub-networks dedicated to the estimation of the probability of occurrence of an event and sub-networks for the estimation of the vertical and horizontal distances in the CPA for a pair of aircraft.

Thus, while the first type of sub-networks is dedicated to the development of the ATM safety barriers model, the second type is aimed at modelling the outputs of the event tree as well as the distribution of the vertical and horizontal separation in the CPA of all the aircraft pairs included in the sample.

The input variables of the subnetwork are defined by traffic states or conditions of the scenario in question. These are modelled as probability distributions based on the actual data.

Figure 6. Bayesian Network Scheme.

The relationship between variables or precursors will be reflected in the table of conditional probabilities, thus capturing the causal relationship between them. The sub-network will learn from this table allowing the prediction of the probability distribution of the outcome variables.

It is relevant to note that the behaviour of the ATCo through the recorded data will infer about this Bayesian Network model.

The outcome of the first type of sub-network is defined by a binomial variable representing the probability of failure or success of each of the barriers of the model, for example, the probability of conflict detection. On the other hand, the output of the second type of sub-network is the probability distribution of the vertical and horizontal separation between aircraft pairs at the Closest Point of Approach obtained as a weighted average of the branches of the event tree, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Model outcomes.

4. Conclusions

The result of the model developed so far is attached in the form of a triptych in Figure 8. This triptych is a graphical and schematic summary of the inputs and results of the model.

The inputs to the model are characterised by probability distributions and refer to the characterisation of a sector through its general conditions and traffic. Examples of these input variables and their corresponding discretisation are included, such as the distribution of FL or aircraft speeds at the entrance of the sector and are represented on the left side of the figure.

On the other hand, the outputs of the network are characterised by probability distributions and can be located either in the centre or on the right-hand side of the triptych. Thus, the central part of the image shows the probability of success of the ATM barriers for a particular state of the input variables, e.g. the probability of interaction or potential conflict between aircraft.

Also for a fixed state of the input variables, the predicted probability of the vertical and horizontal separation distribution of the aircraft pairs at their respective Closest Points of Approach is obtained. In this case it is captured on the far right-hand side of the triptych.

Figure 8. Triptych of the Safety Analysis.

Therefore, with the computational power obtained, the network allows conclusions to be drawn on the consequences and impact of a possible change in the model input conditions on the effectiveness of the ATM safety barriers. The impact on the final distribution of distances in the CPA of the aircraft pairs would also be known, thus allowing the estimation of the probability of a Separation Minima Infringement.

A backward and forwards analysis can also be carried out on the network. Thus, in a backward analysis, the model will be able to deliver a particular configuration in the input variables by setting the outcome variables to a target value. In forward analysis, the model can predict the outcome variables by setting the probability distribution of the input nodes.

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